

ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS THROUGH PRESERVATION OF THE ENVIRONMENT AND ITS SAFETY

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Abstract. *This article is about environmental education for elementary school learners on protecting the environment and its safety. The ecological danger in the environment of the Mother Planet, environmental degradation, the damage is caused by humans.*

Keywords: *ecological crisis, environment, environmental education, space and biosphere, agriculture, social protection, nature and man, water, flora and fauna.*

In the introduction of the article, environmental problems have become a global problem in world science. Therefore, not only one or two countries, but also many countries that are thinking about the balance of the world around us, are focusing on solving this problem. Today, the environmental crisis and problems that are spreading around the world indicate the need to have a proper attitude to nature, to increase attention to it. In particular, solving this problem has risen to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan.

At the current stage of the development of the nations of the world, the issue of improving the mechanisms of ecological education by protecting the environment and its safety in elementary school is becoming an increasingly urgent problem. The environmental danger polluting the environment of the mother planet, the disruption of the "Nature-Society-Human" relationship forces all the peoples of the earth to think about it more deeply. From this point of view, today it is the demand to provide environmental education. Improving the mechanisms of environmental education for students by protecting the environment is being studied as one of the global environmental problems, analytical approach to its content, showing its specific features and scientific research are of great importance.

As we pay attention to the theoretical processes of the article, it is necessary to systematically solve them on a deep scientific basis, since environmental problems, in general, have a complex, comprehensive description that covers all areas of human life. It is necessary to look at the essence of concepts such as "ecology", "environment", "culture", "environmental safety".

The word ecology is derived from the Greek words oikos - "home" and logos - "science, teaching", and is a science that studies the interaction of living organisms with each other and with the environment, as well as the relationship between organisms in the universe and the biosphere. This term is a new term introduced to science by the German biologist Ernst Haeckel (1834-1919) in 1866-1869. Ecological awareness, environmental education through environmental protection. Simple standards of ecological culture have existed since ancient times, in historical written sources, for example, in the sacred book of the Zoroastrian religion "Avesta", in the sources of Buddhism, Christianity, Islam and other religions, as well as in the East Abu Nasr Farabi ("Kitab al-mabodi al-insonia"); Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi ("Kitab surat al-arz" "Image of the Earth" or "Geography"); Abu Rayhan Beruni ("Monuments left from ancient peoples"); Ibn Sina

("Classification of mental sciences") and in the middle ages Alisher Navoi's works such as "Farhad and Shirin" and "Sabai Sayyor" contain information about the world of the human psyche.

Providing environmental education to the young generation entering the society today is one of the vital issues, one of the system of purely biological sciences, and its content is expanding more and more. This situation is explained by the negative impact of modern science and technology development on the environment. Even the globalization of environmental problems is the reason for the use of the term "Human ecology" in science.

In the leading scientific research institutes and centers of Switzerland, Iceland, USA, Japan, South Korea a lot of research is being carried out on the development of environmental education and the re-examination of the scientific-theoretical methods of personnel training in the field of ecology and environmental protection. As a result, in many developed countries, the principles of environmental culture are being introduced in all areas of environmental protection, as well as service provision, agriculture, social protection and sustainable development.

In recent years, "sustainable development" has been intended to explain and teach the sustainability of human life. At the current stage of the development of the nations of the world, the issue of living in an ecologically safe space for mankind is becoming an increasingly urgent problem, and at the same time, the ecological danger polluting the environment, the breakdown of the "nature-society-human" relationship forces us all to think about it more deeply.

The integration of world science and the exchange of experiences on the stabilization of environmental education provide a good opportunity. For example, educational centers devoted to various problems of ecology operate in the USA, dozens of monographic works are published every year, and at the global level, environmental education is recognized as the main issue of teaching the next generation about environmental education. It interprets security as human security, and in this regard, environmental protection is considered as an important source of environmental education.

The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, expressed the following comments on the problem of ecological security: "The problems of ecological security have already gone beyond the national and regional framework and become a common problem of all mankind. Nature and man interact on the basis of certain laws. Violation of these laws will lead to irreparable environmental disasters."

All over the world, mankind is trying to extract as much as possible from nature in order to ease and improve its way of life. It is interesting that people violate nature, but they dream of a clean atmosphere, clean running water, and a long life. In fact, he does not think that he is polluting the environment and acting contrary to his wishes and dreams, and he does not understand that he is gradually becoming a biological victim of economic development. To protect from such a situation, they provide environmental education through elementary schools and they will give good results.

Diseases related to the respiratory tract and lungs are developing due to environmental damage and atmospheric pollution. Continuous human intervention in the oceans and seas is causing the destruction of living organisms there. As a result of chemical substances being thrown into the water, oil and other substances spilled due to the accident of large tankers, the water becomes dead water as a result of the instant death of all the organisms in the water. Already, the lack of environmental knowledge in people has caused serious attacks on human security for

centuries. Therefore, from the first days of independence in our country, attention was paid to this issue at the state level, and many decrees and decisions were adopted.

As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov noted, "Ecology is one of the large-scale social problems of our time. Its solution is in the interests of all nations, and the present day and future of civilization largely depends on the solution of this problem."

In the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the Second International Summit "Cooperation for Green Growth and Global Goals-2030": "For the development of our Motherland, to improve the scientific environment in our country, especially to strengthen the desire for science among young people, to further develop the scientific, technical and innovative fields "We will do many good things in the future" [19], which shows how truthful they are. Because based on these ideas, it is important to create teaching mechanisms based on an interdisciplinary integrated approach in the primary education system, increase the ability to apply scientific knowledge in everyday life, and improve the system of preparing young generation for the formation of natural science literacy. There are serious deficiencies in nature protection and preservation of ecological balance, use and protection of land, water, terrestrial resources - forest, air, flora and fauna, and medicinal plants. As a result of serious changes in the relationship between man and nature, man's desire to dominate nature, the concept of "equilibrium stability" has gone out of circulation, the emergence of a crisis situation on our planet and the threat to world civilization are increasing more and more.

This requires mobilization of "ecological education" to the problem of ecological crisis, revision of state and society's legislative projects in this field, and coordination with the interests of humanity.

Therefore, in the face of global environmental problems, people should be taught to protect nature from childhood, because many problems related to the environment do not escape any person. In order to understand the ecological disaster caused by the terrible mistakes of the wicked people, air and water pollution, global warming, discharge of household waste, acid rain and the greenhouse effect, the destruction of forests, it is required the formation of a culture of environmental safety and the acquisition of modern knowledge. Ongoing global warming and accompanying climatological changes are likely to have serious negative environmental consequences in the near future. The increasing number of warm periods is changing water storage cycles, leading to more extreme weather events, longer droughts and heavier precipitation, and is expected to wreak havoc on glaciers and snowpacks, which play a role in the natural moderate management of water flows in ecosystems.

Primary education is aimed at forming the foundations of literacy, knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for students to continue general secondary education [3]. It is necessary to carry out ecological safety culture in a coherent manner at all stages of continuous education. After all, elementary school students perform tasks related to safe environmental protection in accordance with their age, including the knowledge, skills, competences, competences related to the rational use of drinking water and other natural resources important for human health are improved in the course of classroom and extracurricular education, the environment - the possibilities of using environmentally friendly technologies in practice, which allow to reduce the level of environmental pollution, are taught.

In conclusion, it can be said that, the introduction of economical, environmentally friendly technologies in solving environmental problems, the promotion of ecological culture for students,

the formation of a sense of rational attitude to the environment, the preservation of natural resources for future generations, and the prevention of anthropogenic effects is one of the main factors, in which the importance of environmental education is incomparable, because it occupies an important place in maintaining stability based on ensuring the harmony of the environment and social life through the effective use of nature.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. From national revival to national rise. Volume 4. -Tashkent: "Uzbekistan". -B. 387
2. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev at the second international summit "Green growth and cooperation for global goals-2030" (P4G).
3. Decision PQ-76 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to organize the activities of state bodies in the field of environmental protection and environmental control". PQ-76 No. 30.12.2021. (lex.uz).
4. Ecological culture is the work and human duty of all of us. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the meeting of video selectors on the priority tasks for 2022 on the improvement of the waste management system and the improvement of the ecological situation in the regions, the implementation of the nationwide project "Green Space", Newspaper. February 3, 2022 No. 25 (8087).
5. Karimov I.A.. Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threat to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development. -Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan". 1997. -B. 110.
6. Avazov Sh. Environmental education at school. - T.: Teacher. 1992. - 62 p.
7. Aidarov E.B. Environmental education of students by protecting the environment.-T.: Ilm-ziya. 2014.- 231b.
8. Zverev I.D. Ecology and school education. - M.: Znanie, 1988. – 96.
9. Isakulova N.J. Scientific-pedagogical bases of formation of concepts related to environmental education among elementary school. DISSERTATION written for obtaining the scientific degree of Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences. - T., 2006. - 186 p
10. Turdikulov E.A. Environmental education among elementary school . -T.: Teacher, 1991. - 192 p.
11. Khudaikulov H.J. Water is the source of life. "Primary Education" magazine. -T.: 2004.-28-29-p.